

NATIONAL REALMES IN THE TRANSLATION OF TOURISM TERMS

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Annotation: in this article investigated and analyzing the comparative analysis of the national realmes in the translation and terms of tourism in English, Russian and Uzbek. It is devoted to the comparative study of tourist terminology systems in English and Uzbek through Russian: tour operator, caravanning, familiarization tour, booking, travel fair, travel agent, tourist service provider, resort, motorhome, transportation, etc.

Key words: tour operator, area, familiarization tour, hosting, travel fair, travel agent, tourist service provider, resort, guest.

A number of studies have been made in the field of philology, including the realities of language, literature and translation studies and their translation from one language to another. Among them, Akhmanova O.S., who studied realism in linguistics and gave scientific definitions, Vazburd V.M., a Russian scientist who studied it in the field of country studies, Vereshagin and Kostomarov, who studied it from the point of view of cultural studies, Kunin A.V. is one of the interesting studies. The important book of Bulgarian scientists Vlahov, Florin S., who analyzed scientifically from the point of view of translation studies, is of particular importance. From Russian scientists. The work of V. G. Chernov is noteworthy for the fact that the issue of translating realisms from Russian to English is thoroughly researched. Realities from other concepts.

Russian scientist Sapogova L.I. , and there are also certain works on the translation of realisms from Russian to French. Uzbek translators G. Salomov, N. Komilov and Faizullayeva R.'s cases have been treated to a certain extent. Then the difference of realism from other terms, thematic features of realism in languages, and problems of translation into other languages are studied.

The word realema is derived from the Latin realia, which means material, real. In the dictionary of linguistic terms, it is defined as follows: "The result of material culture in existence, and in classical grammar, it is called a linguistic unit that expresses the state formation of a certain country, the history and culture of a certain nation, and the features of communication in a certain language.

There are words in foreign languages that are different in translation entered the languages and became assimilated. The realma of the Russian ruble has become the ruble of the Uzbeks. Also, the European Euro (oyro) has been adopted as Euro in the Uzbek language. This is actually a phenomenon related to the rules of pronunciation. It should be noted that it was appropriated. They are still actively used today.

Translation methods such as transcription, transliteration, interpretation, explanation, interpretation, and the use of alternative options are effective methods of translating Uzbek realities into English. When using such methods, translators are required to pay attention to the author's purpose of using this realma instead of the context.

In translation studies, the problems of translating realities from one language to another have been actively studied. Because of any translational analysis of this issue in dedicated works, one or another attitude is expressed. This problem is distinguished by the fact that a lot of in-depth research has been carried out in European translation studies. In this regard, G. Salomov, R. Faizullayeva, O. Kade, J. Munen, I. Levi, L. Barkhudarov, A. Fedorov, L. Sobolyev, and especially, as mentioned above, by S. Vlahov and S. Florin - Not being a translation in translation books known as are important.

The state of California in America is known for its big cities, Hollywood film town, San Francisco, Los Angeles. That's why when talking about California - meeting with California - freeway realities. Freeway is freeway in English, that is, free, empty; way means road. More precisely, without any traffic lights means the way. Such notes and comments are important for both the translator and his reader. Only such explanations we will be able to learn the essence of realities with this tool. It should also be noted that there are significant differences between the realities of American English and British English. Because even if they speak the same language, they are considered to be peoples belonging to different conditions and mentality.

In tourism terminology, or more generally, in translation, Realia (plural noun) are words and expressions for the tangible elements of a culture. The word realia comes from medieval Latin, originally meaning "real things," meaning things that exist as opposed to abstract things. The Bulgarian translators Vlahov and Florin, who were the first to carry out an in-depth study of realma, created the modern meaning of the word. They show that because

realism has a very national tone, they often pose a challenge for translation. Realism should not be confused with terminology: terminology is used in scientific literature to designate things related to the scientific field, and is usually used only in other types of texts to serve a very specific stylistic purpose. Fiction loves realism for the exotic look it brings. Realia types and examples | Vlahov and Florin divide them into different categories:

Geography

- physical geography: fjord, mistral, steppe, tornado, tsunami, etc
- Geographical objects related to human activity: polder, etc
- endemic species: kiwi, koala, sequoia, abominable snowman, etc

Ethnography

- everyday life: paprika, spaghetti, empanada, cider, bistrot, sauna, kimono, sari, sombrero, jeans, igloo, bungalow, etc.
- work: carabinieri, concierge, machete, etc
- arts and culture: cowgirl, tarantella, banjo, gong, commedia dell'arte, harlequin, bard, geisha, ramadan, cinco de mayo, easter, santa claus, vampire, mormon, quaker, etc.
- ethnic characteristics: cockney, fritz, gringo, yankee, etc.
- measurements and money: mile, kilometer, hectare, gallon, perch, sum, tenge, ruble, lira, peseta, talent.

Politics and society

- administrative divisions: region, province, department, state, district, canton, principality, favela, bidonville, souk.
- Bodies and functions: agora, forum, knesset, дума, senate, chancellor, king, shah, pharaoh, minister, ayatollah, satrap.
- Political and Social Life: Peronist, Tupamaros, Ku Klux Klan, Partigiani, Slav, Lobby, Lord, Bolsheviks, Aggregé, Samurai, Union Jack, Fleur-de-lis
- military realia: cohort, phalanx, arquebus, AK-47, Katyusha, cuirassier

2) Transcription according to the pronunciation rules of the learned language. For example, the Hindi word कश्मिर becomes kachemir in French.

3) Creating a new word or calque, for example English flea market inspired by French marché aux puces

4) Creating a new word that is similar to the original word but has its own gloss, for example muezzin from Arabic mu'adhdhin

5) Using a different but related word from the source language, passing it off as the original word. For example, the Italian word for cappuccino is often translated into English as latte, which means "milk" in Italian.

- 6) Clarifying the meaning of Synagogue as Jewish synagogue
- 7) Replace the word with a similar local word, for example French art nouveau (literally "new art") for Jugendstil
- 8) Substituting a generic or international word, eg red wine for Beaujolais.
- 9) Adding an adjective to help the reader identify the origin of the element of realia, as in the Argentine pampas

In order to avoid the ambiguities that might arise from using more culturally neutral translations, adequacy is often prioritized over acceptability for non-fiction today - although the opposite has prevailed in the past. In addition, consideration should be given to how the element of realia relates to its respective culture in terms of importance and familiarity. If, for example, it is very common in the source culture, then providing an adequate translation creates an exotic note that was not there in the first place.

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